

THE HE ENICON AND EXCEED PROJECTS. OBJECTIVES AND AMBITION TOWARDS CLIMATE NEUTRALITY

by

Lefteris Doitsidis¹, Anna Kritikaki¹ and Kostas Komnitsas¹

¹*Technical University of Crete, GR-73100 Kounoupidiana, Chania, Greece*

E-mail (L.D): edoitsidis@tuc.gr

Overview

The transition to a climate-neutral society by 2050 is both a critical challenge and an opportunity to build a better future for all. This objective is at the heart of the European Green Deal and in line with the EU's commitment to global climate action under the Paris Agreement. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA) the demand for nickel (Ni), cobalt (Co) and lithium (Li), will increase 21, 19 and 42 times respectively, within the next 20 years (IEA, 2021).

If no action is taken, Europe will almost certainly see demand outstripping supply. What makes matters much worse is that the Ni/Co mining/processing/refining value chains are concentrated in the Democratic Republic of Congo (Co mining), Indonesia (Ni mining and refining based on High-Pressure Acid Leaching, HPAL), and China, whose role is rapidly growing. Also, Europe has a minor role in the rapidly expanding global Li value chain for mining and refining and is 100% reliant on its import (EU, 2020). ENICON and EXCEED HE projects aim to increase the involvement of Europe in the global value chains for energy transition metals. Both projects also participate in the Cluster Hub "Production of raw materials for batteries from European resources", a knowledge exchange platform facilitating collaboration among research institutes, industry and innovation stakeholders towards the production of raw materials for battery applications from primary and secondary resources available in Europe and the recycling of batteries, <https://www.materialsforbatterieshub.eu/>.

ENICON HE project, <https://enicon-horizon.eu/>

Europe faces a major challenge to ensure reliable, affordable and sustainable supplies of Ni and Co (i.e., Class-I Ni: > 99.8 wt% Ni, synthesised into battery-grade NiSO₄, and battery-grade Co, CoSO₄). The global state-of-the-art Ni/Co processing involves production of nickel from sulphidic Ni/Co ores and lateritic (oxidic) ores, while cobalt is a by-product of copper or nickel mining. Pyrometallurgy is the main technology used for treating high-grade sulphide concentrates (e.g., 7-11 wt% Ni). The Ni/Co concentrate is converted to a Ni/Co-rich sulphide matte (~70 wt% Ni) that is subjected to hydrometallurgical treatment with solvent extraction and electrowinning to produce battery-grade Ni and Co. Compared to its laterite competitors, the carbon footprint for this route is low (i.e., < 10 kg CO₂ per kg Ni). The drawbacks are large Co and Ni losses during flotation and converting/smelting, and the generation of a Ni/Co-containing slag. These drawbacks are tackled efficiently in ENICON.

Compared to Ni/Co-sulphidic ores, Ni/Co-lateritic ores are lower grade and mineralogically complex. In Europe, laterites are processed with a pyro-flowsheet, by ENICON partners Larco and Euronickel, into a FeNi (Class-II Ni) product (for the stainless-steel industry). Apart from having a large carbon footprint (Bartzas and Komnitsas, 2015), the drawback of this process is its inability to produce battery-grade Ni (Class-I Ni). Also, this process generates slag that it may be disposed of in landfills and fails to valorise the Co that largely ends up in the FeNi (it contains 0.6-1.0 wt% Co). In the near future, as sulphide reserves are becoming depleted, increased focus will be on the processing of laterites (Harris, 2019).

In contrast, Indonesia, the global Ni powerhouse, uses the HPAL process for laterite ores, that involves high pressures (e.g. 44 bar) and temperature (> 250 °C) during the H₂SO₄ leaching and consumes chemicals to regulate the pH and precipitate the so-called Mixed Hydroxide Precipitate (MHP), that is then re-dissolved in acid in the downstream hydro-processing to produce the battery-grade Ni (and Co).

EXCEED HE project, <https://exceed-horizon.eu/>

There are two primary sources of Li: brine deposits (salars), in which the Li grade is ~0.1 wt% Li₂O; and hard-rock deposits, with higher Li grade, 0.6–1 wt% Li₂O. Li mining is concentrated in just four countries: Australia (hard-rock mining, cf. Greenbushes), Chile & Argentina (cf. salar de Atacama) and China (cf. salars in Qinghai-Tibet plateau). Of even greater concern, the downstream processing and refining of battery-grade Li salts (e.g., LiOH·H₂O, Li₂CO₃) is dominated by just one country, i.e., China (Tadesse et al., 2019). Thus, as Maroš Šefčovič, Vice-President of the EC, mentioned in his keynote speech at the Raw Materials for Europe Conference in Prague, Sep. 12, 2022 “The EU currently supplies only 1% of its own needs for key battery raw materials, such as lithium, cobalt and nickel..... With raw materials becoming the world's most sought-after commodities due to their fundamental role across our economies and societies, we must throw all our weight into secure and sustainable access of raw material”.

Even though 27 hard-rock deposits have been identified in Europe – representing a resource potential of 8.8–21.7 Mt Li₂O – Europe has no major Li mining or refining (Gourcerol et al., 2019). It is true that EXCEED partner Keliber expects to commission a Li plant in Finland in 2024. But this single operation, which received a mining permit from the Finnish Safety and Chemical Agency (TUKES) on March 24, 2022, will not be enough to ease Mr Šefčovič’s worries.

The EC and key actors in the European Battery Alliance have all emphasized that the primary mining of Li must begin in Europe. But apart from the Nordic countries there is little public interest for mining. Lithium projects in Portugal face strong opposition from several stakeholder groups. End of May 2023 it was announced that the Portuguese authorities approved the environmental impact assessment (EIA) for the Mina do Barroso spodumene mine project, owned by Savannah Resources and located in a world heritage site for agriculture. Portugal is Europe’s biggest Li producer, which is used almost exclusively in the ceramics industry. The decision of the Serbian government in January 2022 to block the Rio Tinto Li-mining project in Jadar, was also the result of public opposition. Opponents of Li mining stress the need for more Li-recycling capacity in Europe, so that primary mining is avoided. However, the reality is that by 2040, recycled quantities of Cu, Li, Ni and Co from spent batteries could reduce their primary supply requirements by only ~10%, thus most European Li needs will be covered from primary resources, i.e., salars and hard-rock deposits. In Europe, which has nothing like the salars of Chile or Argentina, this will mean hard-rock deposits, supplemented by geothermal brines (of which there are limited reserves) and secondary Li-bearing resources.

EXCEED aims to move from single-metal Li mining to zero-waste, multi-metal/mineral mining. This needs to be coupled with sustainable mineral processing, leading to a suite of critical metals and minerals derived from sustainable metallurgical extraction and refining processes. As visualised in the Graphical Abstract (**Figure 2**), EXCEED will recover CRMs (Nd/Pr, Nb, Ta, W, Be) and industrial minerals (quartz, feldspar, micas) as by-products from Europe’s foremost Li hard-rock projects. EXCEED’s case studies are two spodumene-bearing lithium-caesium-tantalum (LCT) pegmatite deposits (Keliber’s Rapasaari & Syväjärvi mines in Finland; Savannah’s Mina do Barroso, Portugal) and two Rare-Metal Granite (RMG) deposits (Imerys’ St Austell (UK) and Beauvoir (France) mines).

EXCEED’s multimetal/mineral, zero-waste mining-and-refining approach adopts a mineral-centric, integrated methodology via the application of a first-of-its-kind predictive and forensic geometallurgy, supported by enhanced in-line characterisation tools and the development of digital twins. Using four premier European pegmatite and RMG case studies, EXCEED develops, upscales & demonstrates cost-effective, sustainable and responsible extraction routes for recovering the CRMs and industrial minerals as by-products from Li-bearing hard-rock ores. A suite of CRMs will be extracted and refined, while diverse industrial minerals will be refined and valorised in low-carbon building materials (**Figure 3**). The EXCEED solutions can be replicated for many other European LCT-pegmatite and RMG deposits.

Figure 2. EXCEED's graphical abstract

Figure 3. EXCEED concept: recovery & refining of by-product CRMs (and other metals) along with industrial minerals separation and valorisation starting from Li-bearing pegmatite and Rare-Metal Granite deposits/mines

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